

VOCATIONAL SKILLS TRAINING AND WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AS PANACEA FOR PROMOTING GENDER EQUITY TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH

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ABSTRACT

Poverty represents a principal challenge within the Ghanaian domain particularly among women living in rural areas. In view of this, homes being headed by females are ridden with poverty when compared with that of the households headed by males. As a call by the UN towards sustainable development, vocational skills has been found as a worthy tool capable of empowering and promoting gender equity in the area of poverty reduction in the Ghanaian context. Purposive sampling technique was employed in the selection of 20 interviewees through a semi-structured interview towards eliciting responses for the study. Data obtained from these interviews were transcribed and analysed via thematic analysis so as to provide answers to the research questions. Findings revealed that vocational skills are potent in empowering women and addressing gender inequalities in the Ghanaian context. In addition, it was established that vocational skills can assist in the reduction of poverty among women. Findings also revealed that even though vocational skills training is still informal with its promotion being facilitated by women, who individually double as both workers and trainers. It was concluded that despite how promising vocational skills, several pitfalls were uncovered to inhibit its success amongst women and these include financial challenges resulting in teenage pregnancy, single parenting and non-maintenance of children by their fathers which further culminates into single parenting; all of which has further plunged women into poverty. However, women who have acquired vocational skills should be armed with both financial and logistical support to enable them chart a career in their vocation of choice.

Keywords: Gender equity, Ghana, Sustainable Development, Vocational Skills Training and Women Empowerment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The quest towards empowering women as an avenue for promoting gender equity coupled with the intention for poverty reduction is not a new thing, as this become one cardinal issue ravaging the African continent which is the popularly referred to as “Global South”. In current times, this issue has gained traction internationally especially by feminist organisations as a way of ingraining the rights of women into international agenda to aid development. In this modern era of civilization, women are only able to access to education and trainings in climes like the United States as well as many European nations, as their cultures provide better that enable women to be financial stable and independent; and as a result, take part in decision-making process that translate into sustainable development (Adams & Baddianaah, 2023). However, same cannot be said within the global South especially Ghana, where this study was carried out.

According to Bridges, Bamberry, Wulff and Krivokapic-Skoko, (2022), Poverty arising from both socio-cultural and traditional beliefs has often established male dominance in the Ghanaian societies. The resultant effects of this has been inadequate social services, violence against women and so forth; all of which has become a challenge towards the achievement of fostering gender equity through women empowerment (Gururaja & Osabuohien, 2024). Despite the myriads of challenges identified to be facing the achievement of gender equity and empowerment of women in Ghana, their role as wives, mothers, housekeepers and nurturers of the family are also internal problems limiting their strength (Andiema & Manasi, 2021). Empowerment as a concept has the history that is long and strongly attached to social, status changes as well as the activities directed at empowering women (World Bank, 2021). Empowerment is not really about having knowledge from the realm of academics but to strengthen capacities via other methods like the vocational skills; which is among cardinal backbones of a nation’s economic development. It also plays significant role in narrowing the broad gender equity gap between male and female folks within a society (Mohammed, 2020).

In past years, increasing awareness has been witnessed as interventions targeted towards the improvement of women with poor living status in both urban and rural areas in Ghana. However, according to Rotich, Wanyeki and Dimo, (2020), both socio-cultural and traditional beliefs, which have continuously propelled the dominance of men over the women in the Ghanaian context; thus reflecting a significant setback. This because, most women have become highly vulnerable; due to their lack of access to basic infrastructure like information to enhance their education, adequate healthcare, shelters, properties, even women’s sexual reproductive rights are not catered for or put into cognizance as they do unpaid family work when compared to men and are constricted by traditions and cultural roles (Amankwah, Kodom & Afrane, 2020). Owing to the above stated arguments, this study explored vocational skills training and women empowerment in the global south: a panacea for promoting gender equity towards sustainable development using Ghana as a reference point.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In the Ghanaian society, one major challenge for women and girls in Ghana especially within rural areas. Thus, households headed by females are more than male-headed households, and performing better in poverty ratings as compared with males. This notwithstanding, the incidence of poverty is much more among females than males (Baah-Boateng, 2020). Poverty among women is heightened by the systemic male domination and female subordination, socio-cultural and discriminatory institutions and structures in Ghana that restrict women from access to equal opportunities including productive resources, such as land, credit, and education as well as training opportunities among other support systems. There exists inadequate basic social service such as education, health, water and sanitation in a number of communities to enable the majority of ordinary citizens to have decent livelihood (Ministry of Education, 2021). This obviously is a serious setback to the empowerment of women and gender equity in Ghana. Thus, according Dadzie, Fumey and Namara, (2020), these gender norms and social settings help or hinder the ability of women to benefit from access to resources and development voice.

There are also barriers of empowerment such as lack of information and experience, non-available resources, lack of access to loans and awareness of social or legal structures available for women. This barrier is heightened by the low level of education and literacy rate among women in Ghana. According to a survey conducted by Ghana Statistical Service, funded by the World Bank it reported that 24.9% of female population 15 years and older have never attended school as compared with their male (12.1%) counterparts (Ghana Statistical Service (2017; World Bank, 2020). This finding indeed is a major barrier to empowerment of Ghanaian women to achieving gender equity targets in Ghana. The Ghana Living Standard Survey (GLSS7) conducted by Ghana Statistical Service gathered that 14.1 percent of households in Ghana are headed by females with one or more children compared to only 2.0 percent households headed males.

The survey further posited that 23.7 percent of children are living with only their mother, while 4 percent these children are living with only their father. On employment status, the survey reported that 77.8 percent of females are engaged in vulnerable employment compared to 53.8 percent of males. But in the rural areas, the agricultural sector mostly employed majority of rural dwellers, accounting for 64 percent of those employed (Ghana Statistical Service, 2017). The aforementioned outlooks by Ghana Statistical Service put women in Ghanaian rural societies at disadvantage since agricultural activities in Ghana are predominantly strenuous, manual and involving the use of simple but obsolete farm tools (Ministry of Education, 2021).

Nonetheless, it is reported that nearly two-fifths (38.0%) of females were self-employed in the non-agricultural sector compared to 13.7% of males. This was contained in the Ghana living standard survey conducted by Ghana Statistical Service released in 2017. This implies that Ghanaian women are more likely to be employed in the non-agricultural activities, which include pursuit of skilled based vocation, against their male counterparts. This outlook can be harnessed more in furtherance to achieving targets of gender equity and women's empowerment as Amankwah, Kodom and Afrane, (2020)

argues that economic growth, by reducing poverty and increasing opportunity, can indeed have an important positive impact on gender equity.

It was against these backdrops that this study explored vocational skills training and women empowerment in the global south: a panacea for promoting gender equity towards sustainable development using Ghana as a reference point.

1.3 Objective

Specifically, this study was aimed at:

- i. exploring how women empowerment contributes to gender equity in the Ghanaian domain; and
- ii. ascertaining how training of women in vocational skills contributes to sustainable development in Ghana.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Explanations

2.1.1 Women's Empowerment

Women have the potential to change their own economic states as well as the communities they live in (Amankwah, Kodom & Afrane, 2020), however Bridges, Bamberry, Wulff and Krivokapic-Skoko, (2022) noted that there is a great deal of difficulties explaining empowerment. Thus, empowerment is the processes by which those who have been denied ability to make choices acquire such ability (Bray-Collins, Andrade & Wanjiru, 2022). Again, Bridges, Wulff, Bamberry, Krivokapic-Skoko & Jenkins, (2020). argues that women empowerment is that choices in their lives to acquire that opportunity or control of engagement in decision-making equal as men in all aspects of life social, cultural, politics, economic, environmental and civil.

Britt, (2020) explained that women empowerment as a concept is defined as redistribution of social power and control of resources in favour of women. Further, Bridges, Bamberry, Wulff and Krivokapic-Skoko, (2022) suggested that the concept of empowerment can be achieved through three interrelated fields which are: Agency, Resources and Achievement. Agency represents the processes by which choices are made and put into use; Resources are medium by which agency is exercised and Achievement is the outcome of the agency.

2.1.2 Women and Gender Equity

Kabeer (2016) again identified the causal mechanism of gender equity as “the endless variety and monotonous similarly” patriarchal structures across the world. Gender inequity is a serious phenomenon in many countries especially in Africa which needs to be addressed; it has been attributed to institutional structural barriers. Mason, Mbambo and Pillay, (2018) also supported that the goals of women's empowerment are to challenge patriarchal ideology to transform the structures and institutions that reinforce and perpetuate gender discrimination and social inequity and also to enable poor women to gain access to, and control of, both material and available informational resources.

Customs and customary law have been used as a constitution of cultural authenticity on what is an effect on denial of women rights to property and land for many African women. There is a little prominence of addressing the underlying structural issues driving discrimination and inequity, including violence against women and monished sexual and reproductive rights (Ministry of Education, (2020). Hasin et al. (2018) opine that women constitute more than half of the world's population and what will be the fate of the women when they are lagging behind decision-making participatory on the grounds of social, familiar, economic discrimination.

According to Obiol-Francés, Vergés and Almeda, (2022) women need feminism to advocate for their rights in patriarchal system which subordinates women. Feminism focuses on empowering women to understand the notion that they can hold major key positions in public offices just like men do and encouraging women to be aware of their independence. Mohammed, (2020) argue that the level of access to formal education and socio-economic resources for women is still lower compared to men because of discrimination, women typically do not have access to properties such as land, capital, access to credit, and education than men and, therefore, are less productive in translating their time into cash income for themselves and other household members. To this end, Muhwezi, Aseey, Ondicho and Otieno, (2021) noted that the obstacles women face is due to lack of education, capital, skills, training, access to market in a form of power and inequalities in social relations.

2.1.3 Women Empowerment and Gender Equity

Galea and Chappell, (2022) argue that women's empowerment can also be seen as an important process in reaching gender equity, which is understood to mean that the rights, responsibilities and opportunities of individuals will depend on whether they are born male or female. In furtherance, Gururaja and Osabuohien, (2024) suggest that empowerment is the process of a woman's ability to make "strategic life decisions. From the lens of feminist theory, women's empowerment would function through the resources and access that limit gender disparity and diminish sex inequity. In the word of Hofmann, Zelenka and Savadogo, (2022), women decision-making participation and empowerment are the foundational women's rights to enabling women to have control over their lives and put forth influence in society.

Khan, Aradi, Schwalje, Buckner and Fernandez-Carag, (2018) further explained in her intersectionality views that women of color suffer subordination or discrimination but some black women suffer multiply discrimination on the grounds of race, gender, ethnic, religion, socio-economic class and color. Intersectionality helps us better to understand gender equity and its complexity. It attempts to unveil the processes of subordination and the various ways experienced by the people who are subordinate and those who are privileged by them.

However, Khan, Aradi, Schwalje, Buckner and Fernandez-Carag, (2018) further argues that macro econometrics studies show evidence that gender equity has a positive impact on economic growth to be fairly robust, holding across a range of different countries, time periods and model specifications. In most developing countries, for example, Africa women (including Ghanaian women) are the most vulnerable groups in the society. They

lack access to basic education, information, and health care, and shelters, properties, even to their own sexual reproductive rights as they do unpaid family work compared to men, and are confined to traditions and cultural roles. Discrimination of women has been there for ages, it is inherited from generation to generation so Ministry of Education, (2020) stated that daughters inherit the same levels of discrimination structures that oppressed as their mothers.

2.1.4 Empowerment and Vocational Skills Training

Empowering women is the pathway for accomplishment of all the millennium goals (Ojong, Simba and Dana, (2021). Thus, Ahmed et al (2016) argues that equipping everyone including women with knowledge, vocational skills and skill development for employability will not only bring about development, but will be an agent of change in promoting women's empowerment, and be able to fill in the huge gender equity gap between men and women. This is an effort towards sustainable development. Some research have shown that women who acquire vocational skills, also have improved their socio-economic status as they contribute to home management and these make them financially independent and therefore not vulnerable to men (Olanipekun & Onabanjo, 2020).

Women's empowerment is not necessarily meant academically but in a role of vocational skills as skills (vocational/technical) are the bridge between job and workforce, and this skill development is the key to household productivity, employment, income-generating opportunity for women to boost them for sustainable development (Olanipekun & Onabanjo, 2020). Sohail (2020) mentioned that for the past decade women are performing different kinds of working roles but still they are not equal to men. He said that institutions should be developed for providing equal access for both men and women. There is also a need to create public awareness of women's rights by the help of NGOs and the media houses, policy for gender inequity, access to both education and job opportunity and no payment discrimination at work places and others.

2.1.5 NGOs and Sustainable Development

Rotich, Wanyeki and Dimo, (2020) identified Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) as they perform a variety of service and humanitarian functions, bring citizen concerns to Governments, advocate and monitor policies, and encourage political participation through provision of information. Thus, NGO'S and self-help groups play a very major vital role towards women empowerment by providing basic education, vocational training, training for self-employment, legal aid, and protection for women and self-awareness programs (Sohail, 2020). Manuh and Anyidoho (2010) also highlighted on NGOs in Ghana such as Action Aid Ghana (AAIG), Sinapi Aba Trust, Ghana Congress on Evangelism (GHACOE) and to mention a few play significant roles by using various strategies to promote women's empowerment.

The NGOs engage in vocational skills training in areas such as soap making, beads weaving, slippers making and many more to promote women empowerment and gender equity. Non- governmental organizations are claimed to have impacts on the sustainable development in rural areas of the developing countries, on the other hand noted that all programmes undertaken by NGOs are capable of having positive contributions in the sustainable development process to a certain level (Wignall, Piquard & Joel, 2023).

Furthermore, the Brundtland Commission (WCED 1987) defined sustainable development as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (World Bank, 2021). To achieve the world's development, the UN established The Agenda 2030 sustainable development goals on the success of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG), Wulff, Bridges, Bamberry and Krivokapic-Skoko, (2022) noted that one criticism against the MDGs is that they emphasis planning in top-down processes rather than the agency and participation of the people who are poor but Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) does not leave any country behind.

Sustainable development consists of three main core pillars which are economic development, social development and environmental protection. These 17 common drivers' goals and its targets are used to identify the challenges facing developmental goals. Sustainable Development Goals number 5 seeks to address gender equity and women's empowerment to ensure equal access opportunities for women in political, environmental, economic and social life also this decision- making inclusion equity for women is integral to attaining all the sustainable goals (Jerneck et al. 2017; Razavi 2016).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Women's empowerment is widely recognised as a catalyst for poverty reduction, inclusive growth, and sustainable development. Despite progress, women in the Global South continue to face limited access to education, employment, productive resources, and decision-making power (United Nations, 2020; World Bank, 2022). Vocational Skills Training (VST) has emerged as a transformative intervention for improving women's labour market participation, entrepreneurship, and socio-economic independence (UNESCO, 2021). This study is grounded in four complementary theories: Human Capital Theory (HCT), Feminist Empowerment Theory, Social Role Theory and Longwe Women Empowerment Framework. Together, these theories explain how vocational skills training enhances women's economic and social status, promotes gender equity, and contributes to sustainable development in the Global South.

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory (HCT)

Human Capital Theory posits that investment in education and skills increases individuals' productivity, employability, and earning potential (Becker, 1964; Schultz, 1961). Education and skills acquisition are therefore viewed as strategic tools for economic growth and poverty reduction. Vocational skills training represents a practical form of human capital investment, particularly for women who often lack access to formal higher education in the Global South (UNESCO, 2021). Application of HCT to vocational skills training and women empowerment explains that women's economic marginalisation is largely driven by limited access to skills, education, and labour markets (World Bank, 2022). Vocational training helps bridge this gap by equipping women with market-relevant competencies such as: Technical and vocational skills, Entrepreneurial capabilities, Financial literacy and Digital and employability skills.

These competencies increase women's productivity and income-generating potential, enabling financial independence and reducing poverty (UNESCO, 2021). Human Capital Theory suggests that as women's income rises: Household welfare improves, Children's education and health outcomes improve and Communities experience broader economic growth (World Bank, 2022). Thus, vocational training contributes to inclusive economic development and sustainable livelihoods. Linking this to gender equity and sustainable development, economic empowerment enhances women's bargaining power within households and society. Financial independence reduces dependency and strengthens women's ability to participate in decision-making processes (United Nations, 2020). Consequently, vocational skills training becomes a pathway to gender equality and sustainable development.

2.2.2 Feminist Empowerment Theory

Feminist Empowerment Theory explains empowerment as a process through which women gain resources, agency, and achievements (Kabeer, 1999). The theory highlights how patriarchal structures restrict women's access to education, employment, and economic resources. Empowerment therefore involves challenging structural inequalities and transforming gender relations (Batliwala, 1994). Applying this theory to vocational skills training signifies that vocational training plays a transformative role by: Increasing women's access to economic resources, strengthening agency and decision-making power and Challenging patriarchal labour market structures. Skills training enables women to participate in income-generating activities and male-dominated sectors, reducing gender wage gaps and occupational segregation (Kabeer, 1999).

Vocational training also serves as a tool for gender transformation through vocational skills training, women experience: Increased self-confidence and self-efficacy, reduced financial dependency and greater participation in leadership and community development. Economic independence allows women to negotiate better working conditions, resist exploitation, and influence household decisions (Batliwala, 1994). Thus, vocational training becomes a gender-transformative intervention, addressing structural barriers that perpetuate inequality.

2.2.3 Social Role Theory

Social Role Theory explains how gender roles are socially constructed and reinforced through cultural norms and expectations (Eagly, 1987). In many Global South societies, women are expected to perform unpaid domestic and caregiving roles, limiting their economic participation. These socially constructed roles result in: Occupational segregation, limited labour market access and economic dependency. In terms of the role vocational skills training plays in challenging gender norms, vocational training helps women transition from traditional domestic roles to productive economic roles by providing: Employable skills, entrepreneurship opportunities and access to labour markets. As more women participate in paid work, societal perceptions of women's roles begin to change (World Bank, 2022). It has few implications for gender equity which assist in breaking traditional gender roles leads to: Greater labour force participation, reduced gender stereotypes and increased representation in diverse occupations. Over

time, these changes contribute to gender-equitable societies and sustainable development.

2.2.4 Longwe Women Empowerment Framework

Longwe (2002) developed a gender empowerment framework consisting of five progressive levels: Welfare, Access, Conscientisation, Participation and Control. This framework is widely used to assess women's empowerment in development programmes. When applied to vocational skills training, it contributes to each empowerment level:

- ❖ **Welfare:** Vocational training increases income and reduces poverty among women.
- ❖ **Access:** Training improves women's access to:
 - Education
 - Employment
 - Financial resources
- ❖ **Conscientisation:** Women develop awareness of gender inequality and rights through training and social interaction.
- ❖ **Participation:** Women become active participants in:
 - Economic activities
 - Community leadership
 - Decision-making processes
- ❖ **Control:** Ultimately, women gain control over:
 - Resources
 - Income
 - Household and societal decisions

The Longwe Framework demonstrates that vocational training supports progressive empowerment and gender equality.

2.2.5 Integrating these Theoretical with the Study

Drawing from the four theories, the study proposes that vocational skills training enhances women's human capital, challenges patriarchal structures, transforms gender roles, and promotes progressive empowerment. These outcomes collectively foster gender equity and sustainable development in the Global South.

2.3 Empirical/Previous Studies

Across the Global South, vocational education and training (TVET) has increasingly been positioned as a strategic development tool for tackling poverty, unemployment, and gender inequality. Empirical studies consistently demonstrate that vocational skills training improves women's economic independence, decision-making power, employability, entrepreneurship, and social participation, all of which are key pillars of gender equity and sustainable development. Women's empowerment is widely recognized as both a driver and an outcome of sustainable development, as empowerment enhances women's ability to control resources, make decisions, and participate in economic life.

Numerous rigorous studies show that vocational training significantly increases women's access to decent work and earnings. A landmark randomized controlled trial in Uganda found that young women who participated in the Empowerment and Livelihood for Adolescents (ELA) program experienced: 48% increase in income, 72% increase in self-employment and 26% reduction in early marriage (Bandiera et al., 2020).

Similarly, a meta-analysis of 113 employment programs in developing countries found that skills training programs had stronger employment impacts for women than men, especially when combined with life skills and mentoring (Kluve et al., 2019).

In India, vocational training programs improved women's probability of employment by 18–24%, particularly in non-traditional sectors such as electronics and manufacturing (Chakravarty et al., 2019). African evidence supports this trend. A study in Kenya revealed that vocational training increased women's wages by up to 40% within two years of program completion (Hicks et al., 2016). These findings collectively demonstrate that vocational training is a strong driver of female labour market inclusion.

Many women in the Global South operate within informal economies. Vocational training enhances their entrepreneurial capacity. Research in Ethiopia showed that women receiving TVET training were significantly more likely to start businesses, expand enterprises, and hire employees (Buehren et al., 2017). In Nigeria, skills acquisition programs increased women's business ownership and profit margins, particularly in tailoring, catering, and hairdressing sectors (Adoho et al., 2014). A multi-country World Bank study confirmed that combining vocational skills with business training yields stronger entrepreneurship outcomes than skills training alone (McKenzie & Woodruff, 2017). Thus, vocational training promotes women's economic independence and financial autonomy.

Empirical studies reveal that vocational training enhances women's household bargaining power. Bandiera et al. (2020) found that women in Uganda's ELA program reported increased ability to: make financial decisions, refuse unwanted sex and negotiate marriage timing. In Bangladesh, skills training increased women's participation in household financial decisions by 28% (Heath & Mobarak, 2015). Similarly, a Nepal study found that trained women experienced greater mobility, self-confidence, and social participation (Sharma & Ghimire, 2021). These outcomes highlight vocational training's role in strengthening women's agency and autonomy.

Vocational training programs are also associated with reductions in early marriage and gender-based violence. Evidence from Uganda and Sierra Leone shows that vocational training reduces: early marriage, teenage pregnancy and exposure to domestic violence (Bandiera et al., 2020; Chakravarty et al., 2019). Economic independence reduces women’s vulnerability to exploitative relationships and enhances their negotiating power (Kabeer, 2016).

Vocational training has significant spillover effects on families and communities. Research in Pakistan found that children of women who completed vocational training had: higher school enrollment, improved nutrition and better healthcare access (Azmat & Petrongolo, 2014). In Ghana, women’s vocational training improved household welfare and girls’ educational attainment, contributing to intergenerational gender equity (Darko et al., 2022). Thus, women’s economic empowerment generates multiplier effects for sustainable development.

Skills training enables women to enter male-dominated industries. A randomized trial in India showed that women trained in technical trades were three times more likely to work in non-traditional sectors (Chakravarty et al., 2019). Similarly, Latin American studies found that vocational training reduced occupational gender segregation (Attanasio et al., 2017).

Community perceptions of women’s roles change when women gain skills and employment. In Rwanda, vocational training led to: increased respect for women workers, reduced gender stereotypes and higher female leadership participation (Adoho et al., 2014). These findings demonstrate vocational training’s role in transforming patriarchal norms.

Empirical Evidence on Sustainable Development Outcomes shows that vocational training contributes to multiple Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

SDG	Empirical Contribution
SDG 1 – No Poverty	Increased income and entrepreneurship
SDG 5 – Gender Equality	Enhanced agency and decision-making
SDG 8 – Decent Work	Higher employment rates
SDG 10 – Reduced Inequality	Inclusion of marginalized women

The International Labour Organization confirms that TVET is essential for inclusive and sustainable economic growth (ILO, 2022).

From evidence on Program Effectiveness and Best Practices, research identifies key features of successful vocational programs:

- ❖ **Integrated Training Models:** With programs combining technical skills, life skills, mentoring and financial literacy which produce the strongest outcomes (Kluve et al., 2019).

- ❖ **Market-Driven Training:** With training aligned with labour market demand yields better employment outcomes (World Bank, 2020).
- ❖ **Gender-Responsive Design:** With programs that provide childcare support, safe training spaces and flexible schedules so as to improve women's participation and success (UNESCO, 2021).

2.4 Empirical Gaps Identified in Literature

Despite strong evidence, research gaps remain limited longitudinal studies on long-term impacts, underrepresentation of rural and marginalized women, insufficient evaluation of digital vocational skills and weak integration of climate-related green skills. These gaps justify further research in the Global South context. Empirical evidence overwhelmingly confirms that vocational skills training increases employment and income, promotes entrepreneurship, enhances agency and decision-making, reduces harmful gender practices, supports intergenerational development and contributes to SDGs. Thus, vocational training is a powerful strategy for women's empowerment and gender equity in the Global South.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section described the methodology adopted for the study. It covered the research design, population, sampling and sampling techniques, instrument development, method of data collection, validity and reliability testing, method of data analysis, ethical considerations, and limitations of the methodology.

3.1 Research Design

The researcher adopted the qualitative research design for the study. Bhattacharjee (2012) explain qualitative analysis as the analysis of data (from interview transcripts) and heavily dependent on the researcher's analytic and integrative skills and personal knowledge of the social context where the data is collected. An interpretative paradigm is more productive way to study social order and that is achieved through subjective interpretation of participants involved, such as by interviewing different participants and reconciling differences among their responses using their own subjective perspectives (Bhattacharjee (2012)). The exploratory type of qualitative research design is most suitable for this study. This is so because this study does not seek to predict any cause and effect relationship or talk about correlation, which call for the use of quantitative approach. The study seeks to explain experiences of women engaged in vocation their perception of women empowerment and gender equity, and how vocational skill training contributes to sustainable development. Also, the qualitative research better established the trustworthiness of the study.

The trustworthiness is based on the criteria credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability as espoused by Lincoln and Guba (1985). Credibility addresses the "fit" between "interviewees view" and the researcher's representation of them (Tobin and Begley, 2004), whereas the transferability refers to the generalizability of inquiry, which is achieved in qualitative research through case-to-case transfer ((Tobin and Begley,

2004). The dependability ensures that the research process is logical, traceable, and clearly documented (Tobin and Begley, 2004). The conformability is concerned with establishing that the researcher's interpretation and findings are clearly derived from the responses, requiring the researcher to demonstrate how conclusions and interpretations have been reached (Tobin & Begley, 2004). According to Guba and Lincoln (1989), conformability is established when credibility, transferability and dependability are achieved.

3.2 Data Collection Technique

The study employed a digital interview as the main data collection technique. Semi-structured Interview was conducted based on questions listed in the interview guide (see Appendix for details). The interviewees were guaranteed confidentiality of their responses and sensitive personal information. Interview questions were sequentially posed by the interviewer and certain key words such as women's empowerment and gender equity interpreted to the interviewees in the language they best understand. Interviewees were given enough time to think and reflect on questions asked before they provided responses. Questions were restated or repeated, where necessary for the clarity of the interviewees. Audio recording of the interview was taken to facilitate easier transcription of responses elicited from the interviewees, and to aide data analysis.

3.3 Instrumentation

The researcher administered semi-structured interview questions as contained in the designed interview guide for the study. This was carefully selected by the researcher to achieve two purposes: (1) to help guide the conversation and keep interviewees on the topic; and (2) allows for open-ended responses from the interviewees for more in-depth information. The interview questions were structured into six thematic sections: Demographic Characteristics of Interviewee; Perception of Women Empowerment and Gender Equity; Perception of Vocational Skill Training; Impact of Vocational Skills on Income; Household Decision Making; and Financial and Economic Freedom.

The interviewees of the study were all women, who have either completed vocation training or into vocation practice. The sampled interviewees are made of 4 seamstresses, 4 caterers, 3 bakers and 4 hairdressers. The sample size for the study is 20 interviewees. The rationale was to gather a great deal of information about a small number of people rather than high amount of information about large number of people (Veal, 2006). The emphasis of the sample size was on quality of responses and that explained the 20 interviewees selected for the study.

3.4 Sampling of interviewees

The researcher adopted mixed purposive sampling, comprising of purposive and snowball sampling for the study. The rationale was to ensure the selection of quality interviewees for the study. The researcher used the purposive sampling to select five interviewees, one each from the five sampled rural communities in the district. The purposive sampling allowed the researcher deliberately chooses who to include in the study based on their ability to provide necessary data (Parahoo, 1997). The researcher selected seven (7) women who are into vocation practice from the five sampled communities, and in turn selected the remaining 13 women of same characteristics using

the snowball sampling approach. The seven (7) women purposively sampled were used as referrals to select 10 women of this same ability and characteristics important for the study.

3.5 Pilot-testing

The researcher selected 2 interviewees for a pilot-testing. The pilot-testing was done in order to do test run of digital gadgets (phones and recorder), to ascertain the average duration for each interview and improve familiarisation with interview questions by the researcher and the interviewee. During the interview, attention was given to non-verbal responses body gestures and questioning skills of the researcher. After the pilot-testing, some terminologies as captured in the questions were not accurately translated by the researcher (interviewer). The researcher at certain point in the interview rushed questions on the interviewees, and the digital gadget to be used for the interview went off due to low battery power. The researcher addressed the challenges encountered in the pilot-testing.

3.6 Ethical Consideration

The researcher conducted the study with recourse to ethical considerations and acceptable research standards and practices. In doing so, the researcher first and foremost obtained permission from the University, through the supervisor to conduct the study.

Interviewees' consent was duly sought as their invitation letters were attached to consent forms of the University. Interviewees were given the freedom to respond to all interview questions to the best of their ability and understanding and were not put under any form of compulsion neither the researcher aid them in their responses. The researcher (interviewer) was challenged explaining certain key terminologies to the interviewees, so an interpreter assisted in that regard and translated key words such women's empowerment and gender equity to the understanding of the interviewees. Interviewees were never coerced in order to elicit responses for the study; and none was recorded without their prior approval or consent.

The researcher took steps to ensure the anonymity of the interviewees and confidentiality of their responses for the study. Sensitive personal information was treated as confidential. For example, all data collected was anonymized by replacing the interviewees' names with ascending code numbers (INT 1 – INT 20) in the order of the interviews. Though interviewees freely agreed to be interviewees for the study, they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without questions being asked. Interview date and time was arrived at and interview schedule exclusively prepared upon the approval of the interviewees.

3.7 Data Analysis

The study made use of thematic style of data analysis which translated into thematic coding of data. Firstly, the data collected, which was in audio form, was transcribed into text by adhering to the admonition for a rigorous and verbatim account of the recorded interviews. The recorded interview was manually transcribed from Twi language into English text. The exhaustive nature of the manual transcription process allowed me to

become familiarize with the data through several and repetitive listening of the recorded interviews. In this study, the researcher pre- defined six thematic or categories under which interviews were conducted. The excellence of the research rests in large part on the excellence of the coding (Strauss, 1987) so the pre-defined themes or the categories were intended to facilitate excellent and easier coding. Accordingly the interview transcripts were coded under themes as defined by the researcher in the interview guide so as to make sense out of the data (Creswell, 2014). Since themes were already pre-defined, the study relied on latent coding as suggested by Neuman (2006). This allowed the researcher to capture particular themes, moods, context and implicit communication within the same text.

3.8 Limitations

This sub-section reckons and addresses the constraints encountered in the cause of undertaking this study. The researcher (interviewer) encountered a number of constraints; noticeable among them was the fact she was challenged explaining certain key terminologies as captured in the interview guide for the study to the understanding of the interviewees. Secondly, the interviewees could not express themselves nor clearly understand the English language. As a result, the interviewer was compelled to conduct the interview in Twi language, and this delayed the interview process since the interviewer was also challenged in explaining certain key terminologies. Thirdly, the study encountered unstable network in the interviewees' home country due to the remoteness of their community locations. This also contributed to the delay of the study.

3.9 Analysis and discussion of data

This section of the study dealt with the analysis and discussion of the data collected from the interview conducted. The chapter has been divided into two sections. The first section of the chapter focused on the demographic characteristics of the interviewees while the second section focuses on the analysis and discussion of the study.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section of the study dealt with the analysis and discussion of the data collected from the interview conducted. The section is divided into two sections. The first section focused on the demographic characteristics of the interviewees while the second section focused on the analysis and discussion of the study.

4.1 Demographic characteristics of interviewees

All the interviewees interviewed for the study were women. More specifically, the demographic characteristics were as follows:

Age and marital status

The responses gathered on the age of the interviewees showed that most of the women aged between 31 – 40 years and 20 – 30 years. Only a handful aged between 41 – 50 years. Considering the distribution, majority of the interviewees were active and within the working population. The study also elicited responses to ascertain the marital status of the women. The responses gathered confirmed that majority of the interviewees were

single. The number of the married, divorced and widow women is proportional to the number of women who are single. The researcher observed that the single women all had at least a child they are single handedly providing for them.

Vocation and educational background

On vocation, the responses of the study showed that majority of the women are into seamstress (dressmaking) and hairdressing. Only few were bakers and a caterer. Considering the distribution, all the interviewees were self-employed in the non-agricultural sector. With regards to educational background of the women, the study established that most of the women interviewed had had basic education with few completing secondary education and had no schooling. This distribution showed that the level of education of the women was very low since none had acquired higher education.

4.2 Analysis

The analysis of the study

This section presents the analysis of the study based on the interview conducted. The issues include but not limited to: (i) perception of women's empowerment and gender equity; (ii) perception of vocational skills training; (iii) impact of vocational skills on income; (iv) household decision making, and (v) financial and economic freedom.

Perception of women's empowerment and gender equity.

In finding out how the interviewees perceive women's empowerment and gender equity, the study asked the following questions:

Question1: What is women empowerment to you?

This question was intended to ascertain how the women understand the term women's empowerment. In response, an interviewee remarked that "to me, women's empowerment means as a woman, you must be self-reliant and independent especially from your husband" (INT1). Another also retorted that "I understand women's empowerment to mean the conditions that makes women independent and able to stand out among their colleague women and in the communities, and be able to provide their basic needs themselves" (INT3). It was noted that interviewees viewed women's empowerment from economic perspective.

To them women are empowered when they are gainfully employed and able to provide for themselves without any form of dependence. Interviewees believed that they are empowered by virtue of their vocation which helps them to provide for themselves and other family members. On the explanation of women's empowerment, the study gathered that all the interviewees could not reiterate the meaning of empowerment as outlined in the previous related literatures reviewed. However, the interviewees unanimously viewed women's empowerment as the ability of women to pursue a vocation, be self-reliant, independent and provide for themselves without depending on their husbands or family members.

Question 2: What can be done to empower women in your community?

This question was intended to identify the areas through which women could be empowered in the communities. In response, an interviewee suggested that “providing support for women to pursue vocational skills training, and also assisting women to further their education after completing Junior and Senior High education will help to empower women in my community” (INT3). Another also remarked that “vocational skill training is the way forward to empower women in my community, especially those who could not secure further education at the higher level”. “But they are faced with financial constraints, so assisting them financially can help” (INT6). Women are ready to acquire vocational skills but unable to do so because of financial and logistics constraints. The study gathered from the interviewee that providing women with logistics for their training and financial assistance for start-ups will help to empower women in the communities. The study observed further that majority of the interviewees identified the training of women in vocational skills as the major source of women empowerment in their communities.

Question 3: What are the activities you think empower women in your community? (Can you give me any examples?)

The study asked this question to identify activities that empower women in the communities. Responses gathered from the interview showed that majority of the interviewees identified the employability of women in various vocations as major source of their empowerment in communities. One of the interviewees remarked that “vocational skills training is the major activity that empowers we the women here in this community, and the needed support must be given us to acquire vocational skills” (INT2).

Another interviewee observed that “vocational skill training is the way forward, and that is what most women in my community pursue” (INT3). Another retorted that “we don’t have a busy market in our community due to its remoteness, so it is not lucrative for women in the community to engage in trading.

The best option left is vocation” (INT10). In affirmative, INT11 remarked that “what can empower the women in the community is when we acquire and pursue vocation”. Another interviewee revealed that “some of the women are into farming and trading, so if they could be supported, it would help them a lot” (INT5). INT4 identified peace, employment, good marriage and good living as the activities that can empower women in her community, while INT12 remarked that “acquisition of vocational skills and guidance and counseling for women in my community can help empower them”. The study observed that apart from farming and trading which few of the interviewees alluded to, acquisition and pursuance of vocation by women featured prominently in the majority of the responses elicited.

Question 4: What activities do you think disempower women in your community?

The study asked this question in order to elicit activities that disempower women in the communities. In response, one of the interviewees identified that “teenage pregnancy is a major cause of women disempowerment” (INT14). Another retorted that “we are not getting support financially, and this condition completely disempowers us in the community” (INT11). Another interviewee recounted that “parental care and control is

very poor in my community". "And a lot of girls are not able to acquire higher education". "These are the two major conditions that disempower women in my community" (INT16). INT2 retorted that "we are not getting financial support, and our inability to acquire higher education, and our large family size largely account for our disempowerment in the community". In affirmative, INT6 remarked that "we don't get financial support". "We sometimes obtain financial credit from micro loan schemes, but due to the exorbitant interest charged, we ended up using all our income to service the loans". Another interviewee responded that "our disempowerment is largely due to lack of jobs and non-maintenance of families by our husbands and men who got us pregnant". "Men who impregnate us refuse to accept responsibility of their children, so single-mother parenting is a major challenge faced women here, and this obviously disempowers the women in my community" (INT12). The study identified that lack of financial support, teenage pregnancy and single mother parenting and inability of women to acquire higher education account for the disempowerment of women in the communities.

Question 5: What is gender equity to you?

The study further posed this question to ascertain the understanding of the interviewees on gender equity. In reaction, an interviewee remarked that "If women are given financial and employment opportunities just like men, women would be equal with men". "If they have job to do, they will earn money for themselves, support and take care of their families". "Women would then earn respect from their husbands" (INT2). Another interviewee is of the view that "gender equity means the ability of women to play the men-like role equally as men do when giving the opportunity". If men can build, women can also do, if men can drive, women can also do..." (INT17). Majority of the interviewees viewed gender equity from economic perspective. To them, gender equity is the ability of women to work and provide for themselves without depending on their husbands and their families. It is further noted that the interviewees viewed gender equity as the ability of women to play the men-like role and pursue vocations perceived to be men related, and be positioned to provide for themselves and the family.

Question 6: What is your view on the saying that women empowerment promotes gender equity?

The study posed this question in order to measure how women empowerment promotes gender equity. Responses by interviewees overwhelmingly admitted that women's empowerment promotes gender equity. An interviewee remarked that "women's empowerment promotes gender equity because women who are empowered are not subject to discrimination and violence from their husbands" (INT9). Another interviewee responded that "women's empowerment promotes gender equity, not to the extent of been equal with men in terms of physical strength, but it helps us to be positioned, so that we can provide for ourselves and support our husbands" (INT18). The study gathered that majority of the interviewees affirms that women's empowerment indeed promotes gender equity especially in the area of economic empowerment. The study observed that women who have vocation are able to earn income to meet their personal needs and that of their families. The study again noted that women who are empowered, by virtue of the vocations they pursue, are not subject to discrimination and violence by their husband, but were also positioned to provide for themselves and support their family.

Perception of vocational skills training

In order to ascertain the understanding of vocational skills training, the study asked the following questions:

Question 1: When we mention vocational skills training, how do you understand it?

This question sought to find out the understanding of women on the term vocational skills training. From the responses gathered, the study observed that all the interviewees demonstrated strong understanding of term vocational skills training. All the interviewees understood vocational skills training to mean the acquisition of employable skills that predominantly entails handiwork or handicraft. An interviewee remarked that “it is when you acquire training on how to create something with your hand and sell to people to earn income” (INT19). Another interviewee said “I understand it to mean a skill that cannot be taken away from you because they are on your figure tips. It will be with you until death, and you can use it whenever you feel you want to work with it and earn income” (INT12). Another interviewee also understands vocational skill as “when one has his own vocation, and uses her hand more to create a craft or design something for people to buy. The skill is your own and you can pursue it wherever you go. Can even train your children as well” (INT6). The researcher noted that vocational skill is a skill that when acquired becomes inherent of women, and cannot be taken away from them nor erase from their minds. The study further observed that the interviewees view vocational skill training as an alternative source of livelihood for women who are not academically endowed and those who could not pursue higher education.

Question 2: Can you identify four vocational skills that women in your community pursue?

This question was meant to identify various vocations pursued by women in the communities. In response, the interviewees identified baking, seamstress (dressmaking), hairdressing and catering as the predominant vocations of women in their communities. One of the interviewees remarked that “in my community, I think the vocations that a lot of women are engaged in include seamstress, hairdressing, pastries making and soap making” (INT20). Another interviewee responded that “over here, seamstress and hairdressing is common, and they are the only vocations that pay a lot, so most women here prefer to train in dressmaking and hairdressing so that they can guarantee employment after their training” (INT4). Baking, seamstress (dress making), hairdressing and catering services are the most common vocations that women enroll as apprenticeship trainees. The study further gathered that some women are into trading, pastries, soap and beads making, these vocations are rarely acquired and pursued by the women. Baking, seamstress (dressmaking), hairdressing and catering service are most sought after vocations, and this is attributable to the fact that they deal with necessities of life.

Question 3: What benefits women in your community stand to gain after pursuing vocational skills training? (Can you give me any examples?).

This question was meant to identify benefit women have gained after pursuing vocational skills training. In response, the interviewees identified employment and ability to earn income as immediate benefits. One of the interviewees remarked that “the benefits are plenty to count”. “The women will be self-reliant financially because they will work with

their skills and earn some income". I have gain recognition and respect in my family because my family members see that at least I bring something home at the end of the day". And I am able to provide my personal needs by myself" (INT2). Another also said "I can bear witness that all the women I know in this community that have acquired vocational skills are self-employed and earning money from their work. They have all set up their shops and that alone is refreshing and motivating. The vocations bear testimony for themselves, and that motivate the young girls here also to acquire a vocational skill" (INT3). Some of the benefits include self-employment either providing related services or set up apprenticeship training center for trainees. It is also noted that women with income earned regular income and are able to provide their personal needs without any dependence on their husbands or family members.

Question 4: Do you agree that women in your community can be employable after acquiring vocational skills? Give reason(s) for your answers.

The study asked this question to find out the available employable opportunities for women after acquiring vocational skills. On the issue of whether women who enroll in vocational skill apprenticeship training are guaranteed job and employment after their apprenticeship training, majority of the interviewees responded in affirmative. An interviewee mentioned that "yes, then are employed. You become self-employed and there is no profession that can offer the best job guarantee than this. All the women I know they have acquired vocational skills are striving to setup their shops. Some even start working from home, and gradually save toward setting up their shop, so for job guarantee, I can assure you that vocational skills provide one" (INT20). Another interviewee retorted that "what is more fulfilling is the fact that once you complete apprenticeship training, you also become an apprenticeship training facilitator. A lot of young girls enroll under you for their training, and that in itself is self-fulfilling" (INT6).

The study observed from the responses of the interviewees that there are ready jobs and employments for women after the completion of vocational training. The study further gathered that women who have pursued vocational skills trained are self-employed and majority of them have tens of apprenticeship trainees under their tutelage. The study further ascertained that major constraint is the setting up of shop; however most of them are able to mobilize resources to set up their shops within a year of completion. Others who could not set up their shops operate from homes, and are still making good income for themselves.

Question 5: Acquisition of vocational skills by women can help reduce poverty in your community. What is your view(s) on this statement?

The researcher asked this question to elicit the views of the interviewees on the notion that acquisition of vocational skills by women help to reduce poverty in their communities. The study gathered that majority of the interviewees agreed that vocational skills training help to reduce poverty in their communities. An interviewee responded that "once, we have secured job out of our vocational skills, we are in good position to fight poverty". "We are assured of some income at the close of work every day". "I admit that poverty conditions are common in my community but those of us with vocation are making earns meet" (INT2). Another said "yes, it can reduce poverty. I used myself as

example, I am able to make earnings meet". I am able to feed myself and my child, and provide all our personal needs". "Talk of clothing, shelter and other needs for survival". "Though I am not accounted amongst the rich, but I am also not impoverished" (INT4).

Another also remarked that "I agree with you perfectly because our vocation has helped and continue to help us address our poverty burdens". "We have reduced our financial challenge mainly because we earn income from the work that we do" (INT7). The findings from the responses showed that women are able to secure jobs and employment out of vocational training they have acquired, and are in good position to fight poverty. The women are able to meet their needs on daily basis, and reduced their financial challenges due to the fact that they earned income from their vocation on daily basis.

Question 6: Do you think acquisition of vocational skills by women would empower them? Give reason(s) for your answers.

This question was to gather responses to help the study measure the impact of vocational skills training on women empowerment. The study observed that the interviewees overwhelmingly responded that women are empowered by virtue of their vocation. The study further gathered that women with vocation are independent, especially in their marriage, and respected by their husbands and family members. An interviewee remarked that "If you have a vocation, you will develop in life. Besides, one will become independent especially in your marriage. For me, my husband understands and respects me just because I am able to support him providing for the family" (INT2). Another interviewee said "acquiring vocational skill will empower you as woman. You will secure a job, earn income and will be able to provide your needs without necessarily depending on your husband or family for those personal needs. Look at me now, I have a secured job to do, and make money every day. I decide what to do with my money and what to buy and what not buy. So I feel empowered" (INT6).

The study found out that besides the work and money women with vocation make, they are also recognized and respected in their communities. The researcher observed that women with vocation have economic freedom and autonomy. They decided what to do with and how to spend their income.

Impact of vocational skills on income

This thematic category was intended to find out the sources and levels of income of women before and after pursuing vocational skills training: this was measured through the following questions:

Question 1: Before acquiring vocational skills, were you earning income? If YES, what was the source(s) of your income? If NO, is it because you had not acquired a vocation?

This question was intended to aid the study establish the impact of vocational skills on the income levels of women before and after acquiring a vocation. On the issue of source of income, the study gathered that majority of women who are into vocation earn income mainly through their vocation; and that prior to their training, they barely earned income; and where they earned income attributed the source to other family members. One of the interviewees remarked that "perfectly so, the main source of income is the catering

services I provide” (INT9). Another interviewee answered in affirmative “yes, if not the vocation I am engaged in, I would have had no other source that I could explore to earn income”. “I make all my monies from hairdressing work” (INT11). Almost all the interviewees admitted that they had no source of income prior to their vocational skills training.

Question 2: Have you earned or earning income in the past one year after acquiring vocational skills? If YES, what is the main source of your income? If NO, is it because you have not started practicing your vocation?

Regarding the income earning before and after vocational training, the interviewees unanimously retorted how they were virtually on zero income prior to their vocational skills training, and how things have turned around for them after vocational training. One of interviewee remarked that “I was young and had no vocation then, so it is practically impossible to be on a regular income”. I was completely not working so how could I have earned income” (INT6). Another interviewee bemoaned the fact that “the time I had no vocation, I had no income”. Money never came into my hand or purse”. The little keeping money entirely came from my parent” (INT9). Overall, majority of the interviewee admitted that they never earned any regular income prior to their vocational training. However, the interviewees admitted changes in their income status after vocational training. All the interviewees admitted that they are now on regular income after their vocational training. One of interviewees remarked that “though I barely save, I am able to provide for myself and children’s educational needs, and the income I earn is mainly attributable to my vocation” (INT9). Another interviewee also observed that “yes, I have being earning income in the past one year, and I am now able to save towards setting up my shop” (INT4). Over all the findings suggest that women are able to earn regular income from their vocation.

On the level of income after vocational training, there were mixed reactions by the interviewees. While others admitted increase in their income levels, some observed that their income levels remain same over the past one year. An interviewee responded that “yes and sometimes amazed considering all the monies I make from the baking business”. “The increase in my income is amazing” (INT1). Another also observed that “Yes, but it depends on the area where you are working”. “It increases sometimes and other time too decreases, but on the whole, it is better than the time when I had no vocation” (INT7). The study found out that majority of the interviewees overwhelmingly admitted an increase in their income levels while few answered NO, but still expressed optimism that their income level will increase in future.

Question 3: Are you able to buy your personal needs that hitherto, you were unable to acquire because you had no vocation? If YES, do you attribute your ability to buy personal needs now to the vocation you are engaged in? If NO, are you able to buy some of your personal needs?

Another dimension the impact of vocational skills training on income question explored during the interview was the acquisition of personal needs by interviewees. The study observed that majority of interviewees emphatically responded that they are able to

acquire the personal needs and that of other family members through the income they obtained from their vocation. An interviewee remarked that “formerly, I asked my husband for everything I need, including women’s necessities of life, but now I can confidently say that I personally provide for my personal needs, and do not depend on my husband again” (INT13). Other interviewees recounted that “Yes, I am able to buy my personal needs and it is mainly due to my dressmaking vocation” (INT5) and “I don’t only buy my personal needs alone, I am now able to buy things for my children and even husband sometimes” (INT4).

Household decision making

This category was intended to help the study unveils the level of women’s participation in family decision making before and after acquiring and pursuing vocations. The study obtained results through the following questions:

Question 1: Were you helped by your husband or family member in your household duties prior to you acquiring vocational skills?

The study asked this question in order to ascertain information on whether women prior to acquiring vocations were supported in their household duties by their husbands and any family member. The study observed that most of the interviewees recounted that enjoying tremendous support from their family members. They were assisted in household chores throughout the period of their vocational training. One of the interviewees remarked that “yes, I was assisted by my siblings because I always go for apprenticeship training early and come home late, so during the week day almost all the household duties were done by my siblings”. “I only compliment them during weekends” (INT10). Another interviewee also remarked that “prior to my vocational training, I was with my parents, and my mother assisted me in my household duties”. Cooking and washing of dishes were all taken care of by my mother, and I am grateful to her for such support” (INT11). Other interviewee responded affirmatively that “my parents assisted me not only in household duties, but I was a single mother then, so my mother helped me to maintain and care for my child at home” (INT18).

Question 2: Did your husband allowed you or family member allowed you to take part in key family decision prior to you acquiring vocational skills? If YES, what particular decision of the family did you partake in? If NO, were family decisions influenced by factors other than economic reasons? (Can you give me any of such reasons?)

This question seeks to find out from interviewees the level of their involvement in household decision making before acquiring a vocation. The interviewees unanimously answered NO, and affirmed that family decisions were borne out of economic reasons. From the responses, the study observed that majority of the interviewees rarely participated or allowed to take part in family decisions prior to their vocational training. An interviewee responded that “I was not consulted neither did I took part in family decision making”. “I was not even allowed to sit in the meeting because I was treated as a minor and not on income” (INT3). Another interviewee also remarked that “I was even treated with contempt by my elderly brothers”. “They sometimes ridiculed me over not be on any income, and always sacked from family meetings involving financial

considerations" (INT4). The study observed that economic reason accounted for the inability of the interviewees to take part in family decision making prior to their vocational training. They were unemployed and not on regular income, hence their inability to partake in family decision making.

Question 3: Did you contribute financially to the family management prior to you acquiring a vocation? If YES, can you give any item you contributed towards, and what was the source of your income? If NO, is it because you had not acquired or engaged in a vocation?

The researcher asked this question in order to ascertain women's financial contribution towards family management before they acquired or engaged in a vocation. The study observed that the trend was identical to interviewees' participation in family decision making. The interviewees unanimously answered YES admitting their inability to contribute to family management prior to vocational training. One of the interviewees remarked with a rhetorical question "how could I contribute financially to the family management when I was an apprentice"? "It was practically impossible for me" (INT13). Another also reiterated that „it was practically impossible for me to have contributed financially to family management prior to my apprenticeship training". "I was rather dependent on my parents for upkeep and personal needs" (INT15). The study observed that the economic reasons cited for their inability to take part in family decisions accounted same for their inability to contribute financially to family management. The reasons are not far-fetched; they interviewees were simply unemployed and not on income.

Question 4: Now that you are engaged in vocation, does your husband or family member(s) assist you in your household chores? If YES, identify areas that you are assisted by your husband or family member? If NO, are you able to combine your household chores with your vocational practice?

This question of the study was intended to establish whether women with vocation are assisted in their household chores or otherwise by their husbands or family members; and whether the women are able to combine their household management with their vocational practice. The study noted that all the interviewees still enjoy the same support and assistance from their family and husbands even after vocational training. An interviewee remarked that "my siblings assist me in my household duties". "I am the youngest, and considering the nature of my work, they always assist me". "My sister usually cooks and sometimes washes my clothes" (INT5).

Another interviewee responded that "I am extremely fortunate as a woman". "My husband really assists me in my household chores: washing, cooking and cleaning; he does all to support me, and I really appreciate it most". "Had it not been my husband, combining work and household duties would have being a challenge" (INT16). Other interviewee retorted that "Well, with regards to household chores, I receive assistance from my children". "They are in their teen now and are able to prepare dishes and do general household chores" (INT19). The evidence from the responses indicate that majority of interviewees received support from their families prior to vocational training and still enjoy same privilege after training. They are assisted in areas such cooking,

washing dishes, cleaning and fetching children from school. The researcher observed further that the busy schedule of their work strongly accounted for the support and assistance accorded them by their families and husbands.

Question 5: Now that you have a vocation, do you personally take family decision(s) without consulting your husband or family member(s)? If YES, what decision(s) in the past one year, have you taken in the family without consultation? If NO, is it because such decision(s) require(s) consultation with your husband or family member(s)

The study observed, however, from the responses that the interviewee are now able and allowed to take part in family decision making. Remarkably, the study observed that some interviewees take family decisions personally without consultation. An interviewee remarked that “agreeably so, I take decisions without the consent of any family member”. “I solely provide education for my children without assistance or input of any family member” (INT9). Another interviewee also remarked that “I single-handedly enrolled my child in school, provided his educational needs and paid his school fees”. “I never consulted neither any family member nor my husband” (INT18). The study further observed that this sudden ability to take part and make family decisions is attributable to the fact that the interviewees are employed and are on regular income through their vocations.

Question 6: Now that you have a vocation, do you personally acquire family needs/items independently? (Can you give any example?).

This question seeks to measure the ability of women with vocation to acquire personal and family needs independently? The study gathered from the responses that majority of the interviewees are able to acquire personal and family need now that they have vocation. The researcher observed a reversal trend after their vocational training. The interviewees overwhelmingly admitted that they now contribute to family management after vocational training. An interviewee remarked that “I personally acquire personal needs such as food, clothes for my sister, mother and my child” (INT8). Another interviewee also responded that “I sometimes buy groceries for the family”. I recently took a loan for my uncle, and I am servicing it personally and independently” (INT4). Another reiterated “I provide food for my parent on daily basis, I’m able to make such provisions independently and out of the income from my hairdressing vocation” (INT10).

Financial and economic freedom

The financial and economic freedom category was meant to help the study measure the financial and economic freedom of women with vocation. The study obtained results through the following questions:

Question 1: Now that you have a vocation, are you able to buy personal needs that hitherto were bought by your husband or a family member? If YES, identify four personal needs you have bought personally in the past one year. If NO, are able to supplement your personal needs now?

This question was intended to measure the ability of women to acquire personal needs personally after vocational training. The study observed that all the interviewees answered YES indicating that they are able to acquire their personal needs by themselves because they now practice a vocation. One of the interviewees remarked that “I am now able to buy my own personal needs that formerly I was not able to buy”. For one, I am able to buy a parcel of land, and I am molding blocks to start my building project”. “I also set up my shop and paid my rent” (INT2). Another also responded that “I am now able to buy my personal needs: cooking utensils, sewing machine, and clothing” (INT16). An interviewee reiterated that “I have lost count of items and personal needs I have bought with income earned from my vocation in the past one year” (INT10). Other interviewee retorted that “just this year, I have bought these items personally with my own money: television set, ceiling fan, bed, set of furniture, and I have also paid my rent” (INT7). The study observed that women with vocation are economically resourceful, which gives them the ability to acquire their personal needs personally from their own income earned from their vocation.

Question 2: What is your opinion on the view that women who are employed vocationally do not mostly depend on their husbands or any family member for their personal needs?

This question was intended to ascertain information of the independence of women with vocation in the communities. From the responses gathered, the study observed that all the interviewees assented to the opinion that women who are employed vocationally mostly do not depend on their husbands or family members for their personal needs. One of the interviewees remarked that “in my case, the income I earn from my vocation is what I used to buy my personal needs. I do not depend on any family member” (INT11). Another interviewee held that “it is very true that women with vocation do not depend on anyone for their needs”. “In my case, I have a vocation, so I don’t depend on a man for my personal needs” (INT8). Other retorted that “yes, we don’t depend so much on husband and family, but by convention, my husband sometimes voluntarily buys things for me” (INT6).

Question 3: What is your opinion on the view that women employed vocationally are not controlled by their husbands or any family member on how to spend their income?

This question sought to find answers from the interviewees whether their husbands or family members should control how they spend their income. From the responses given by the interviewees, the study observed that all the women interviewed dissented to the view. The interviewees unanimously responded that women with vocation do not mostly depend on their husbands or family members for their personal needs, hence should not be controlled by their husbands or family members on how to spend their income. One of the interviewees recounted that “why should we allow our husbands and family members control our money”? “We do not exert same control over them, so I do not see the need why they should determine how we should spend our income” (INT8). Another remarked that “we work hard for our money, and must have the right to determine how we spend it” (INT6). Other rejoined that “we have worked for our money, so I think we should

equally have the freedom to control our finances". "For me, my husband does not even enquire of the whereabouts of my income" (INT3).

Question 4: What are your opinion on husbands or family members who control finances of women? Do you think women who are pursuing vocation should be given freedom to control their own finance?

The researcher asked this question to find whether women who are pursuing vocation should be given freedom to control their own finances. From the responses gathered, the study observed that all the women interviewed responded that women pursuing vocation should be given freedom to control their own finances. The interviewees fairly responded that husbands and family members should not control finances of women employed vocationally. One of interviewees remarked that "once women are working, they should control their finances themselves". "Myself, I do not allow my husband to control my finances, I rather sometimes consults him on what to do, but he has no right to demand account of my income" (INT6). Another interviewee recounted that "women pursuing their own vocations should not be controlled by their husbands or family members". "I have absolute freedom over my finances" (INT10). Other rejoined by admitting that "you sometimes need control and direction from your husband or family member in regarding your fiancés, however, the control should be moderate" (INT9). INT8 responded that "women sometimes lavishly spent their money, so they should not entirely be allowed to control their finances alone". The study observed that while most of interviewees advocated for absolute control of women over their own finances, few of the interviewees responded that the control should be moderated.

Question 5: In your opinion, do you think women who are vocationally employed should be financially independent? Do you think such women should be allowed to make their own decisions?

This question aided the study to elicit the opinion of the interviewees on financial independence and decision making by women who are employed vocationally. The responses gathered indicated that majority of interviewees responded that women with vocation should be financially independents, and allowed to make their own financial decisions though there should some modicum for consultation. One of the interviewees remarked that "it is good if women pursuing their vocation have financial independence and make financial decisions of their own, but it is equally good to listen to suggestions from their husbands or family members" (INT8). Another interviewee responded that "yes we should be financially independent, but sometimes we can consult our husbands or family members when the need arises" (INT5). (INT6) remarked that "yes because the women know the operations of their vocations, so they are can better decide on what to do with their incomes. Other recounted that "not entirely, because anything can happen, and since two heads are always better than one, it is advisable that we sometimes consult family members on certain financial decisions" (INT3).

Question 6: How do you feel after gaining financial independence and making decisions yourself?

This question sought to aid the study to find out the mood, feelings, and emotional expressions of women with vocation after gaining financial independence taking making decisions by themselves. The study observed that responses by all the interviewees

showed a mood of happiness, comfort and fulfillment of personal goals and development. One of the interviewees recounted that “I am much relieved that I am also counted among the employed in our community, and very excited that I am also recognized and respected in my community” (INT11). Another also rejoined that “I am not worried at all”. “I am very excited that, for one, I can also stand out and be counted”. “I can provide for myself, children and parents without any form of dependence”. “What else will make me happier than this?” (INT10). The study observed that all the interviewees, by their responses, tremendously expressed state of comfort, happiness, satisfaction and excitement, and a sense of personal fulfillment after achieving financial independence and freedom.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the result of the data collected from the field through semi-structured interview to answer the research questions with the view of achieving the objective of the study.

Research Objective One: Exploring how women empowerment contributes to gender equity in the Ghanaian domain.

Research question one sought to find out the contributions of women empowerment to gender equity in Ghana. The following results of the study show that women empowerment contributes to gender equity.

The study confirmed that women who hitherto could not take part in household decision making are able to do so due to their empowerment through vocational skills training. This is in line with findings by Tanu (2016) which suggests that the goals of women’s empowerment are to challenge patriarchal ideology to transform the structures and institutions that reinforces and perpetuate gender discrimination and social inequity and also to enable poor women to gain access to, and control of, both material and available informational resources.

Ahmed et al (2016) argues that equipping everyone including women with knowledge, vocational skills and skill development employability will not only bring about development, but will be an agent of change in promoting women’s empowerment. This is line with the result of the study which confirmed that women with who are vocationally employed are not controlled by their husbands or any family member on how to spend their income. The result further established that women with vocations are economically resourceful, and this gives them the ability to acquire personal needs with their own income. Obviously this is in furtherance of gender equity.

Again, the findings of the study show that vocational skill training is a resource which gives women the power or the ability to achieve women empowerment which translates into economic freedom, independence, financial independence and gender equity. The fact that women are able to take personal and household decisions without consultation from their husbands and family members is in furtherance of gender equity. This confirms the conceptualization of the three dimensions of empowerment as outlined Kabeer (2005), suggests that the concept of empowerment can be achieved through three interrelated fields which are agency, resources and achievement. Agency represents the

process by which choices are made and put into use; resources are the medium by which agency is exercised and achievement is the outcome of the agency.

Research Objective Two: Ascertaining how training of women in vocational skills contributes to sustainable development in Ghana.

This question sought to identify ways training of women in vocational skills be promoted to achieve sustainable development. The results of the study suggest that the establishment of vocational training centers in the communities will help promote the training of women to acquire and develop skills for their sustainability. This result of the study confirms the findings by Narayan (2003) which suggests that poverty and vulnerability will not be reduced without broad-based growth fueled by private sector activity and economic development and growth cannot be sustained if poor people are excluded from optimal engagement in productive activities, thus they lack information, connections, capital, skills, credit, and organization.

The results of the study suggest that the establishment of vocational training centers in the communities will help promote the training of women to acquire and develop skills for their sustainable. The results of study also suggest that provision of training logistics, financial support by Non- Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and self-help groups will play a major in promoting vocational skill training among women in the communities. This confirms the findings that NGOs and self-help groups play a major role towards women empowerment by providing basic education, vocational training, training for self-employment, legal aid, protection for women and self-awareness programmes (Narumugai et al 2019, Ahamed et al 2015).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study was purposely undertaken to examine the role of vocational skills in promoting women's empowerment and gender equity to reduce poverty for sustainable development in Ghana. The study found that women's empowerment directly contributes to gender equity culminating in reduction of poverty conditions faced women with vocation in the district. Additionally, the study found that vocational skills training is a crucial tool for women's empowerment and gender equity, and also contributes to poverty reduction among women with vocation in the district. Again, the study confirmed that vocational skills training are main sources of income for women in the district. However, prevalence teenage pregnancy, low of level of education, single parenting, poor parental care and child non-maintenance are main social constraints faced the promotion of vocational skills training in the district.

The study established that women with vocation are empowered and able to overcome gender inequity conditions in the district. They have access to the right to decision making in their families, and economic freedom and independence which make them capable of providing personal needs for themselves and other family members. This affirms that vocational skills training has helped to achieve sustainable development goal five which primarily focuses on achievement of women empowerment and gender equity. Moreover, the study revealed that in spite of vocational skills training identified as the

main source of women empowerment in the district, its promotion and sustenance has not been given a boost in the district. Apprenticeship training is individually organized by women who double as service providers, and the rippling effect is that few young girls are able to enroll, denying many potential trainees. The study confirmed that formalized vocational school is non-existent in the district.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the results of this study and other responses of the interviewees of the study, the following recommendations were offered.

- i. Local government unit as a matter of urgency should institute a strategy to address low level of education among women in the district.
- ii. Establishment of vocational school or training center should be a topmost priority on the agenda of the local government, non-governmental organizations (NGO) and other women advocate partners.
- iii. Awareness drive on adolescent reproductive health and sex education should be embarked upon earnestly to control the menace of teenage pregnancy.
- iv. The social welfare department and the family tribunal in the district direct their attention and operation on the issue of non-maintenance of children to halt its insurgence and relieves women of associated pressures.
- v. Financial and logistics supports should be provided to enable women pursue their vocational careers.

5.3 Limitation of the Study

This sub-section reckons and addresses the constraints encountered in the cause of undertaking this study. The researcher (interviewer) encountered a number of constraints; noticeable among them was the fact they were challenged explaining certain key terminologies as captured in the interview guide for the study to the understanding of the interviewees. Secondly, the interviewees could not express themselves nor clearly understand the English language. As a result, the interviewer was compelled to conduct the interview in Twi language, and this delayed the interview process since the interviewer was also challenged in explaining certain key terminologies. Thirdly, the study encountered unstable network in the interviewees' home country due to the remoteness of their community locations. This also contributed to the delay of the study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interests

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